

Leden's⁴ methods. The equilibrium ligand concentrations and the degree of complex formation were calculated from Beer's law data. The various functions were constructed and evaluated in the manner stated earlier⁵.

The overall stability constant of the complex was determined by Job's⁶ method and Harvey and Manning's⁷ method. The values of stability constants as evaluated by various methods are compiled in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR V(V)-TMBHA COMPLEX AT 30±1°C

Method	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
Yatsimirskii's	5.11	4.68	9.79
Leden's	4.93	4.64	9.57
Job's	—	—	9.50
Harvey-Manning's	—	—	9.42

It seems from Table 1 that, the overall conditional metal-ligand stability constants as well as stepwise stability constants obtained by various methods agree well with each other.

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Spectrophotometric Studies of Lanthanide Complexes with 1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-Naphthol(PAN) in Water-Ethanol Medium

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SEVERAL reports have appeared in the literature on the studies of the formation of rare earth metal complexes with 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol(PAN) and their extraction from aqueous solution into various organic solvents¹⁻¹⁰. However, conflicting reports appeared in the literature regarding the composition of the extracted species, for example, Shibata⁸ reported a composition of 1 : 2 Navrátil⁴ 1 : 4 while Chang Tiao-Hsu and co-workers⁹ reported a composition of 1 : 3. We described in our earlier communications^{11,12} detailed solvent extraction characteristics and the preparation of lanthanide-PAN complexes in solid state and proposed an octahedral structure with a metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 3. In continuation of our earlier studies, we are now incorporating in this communication the results of our spectrophotometric study of these complexes in water-ethanol medium.

Experimental

Photometric measurements were carried out on Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer and Spekol spectrocoulometer using 1 cm corex cells. A Toshniwal Digital (Model CL 46) pH meter with a combined calomel-glass electrode was used for pH measurements.

Stock solutions of lanthanide metals were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of pure oxides (Apachae Chemicals, USA or E. Merck, Germany) in perchloric acid. The solutions were standardised with a standard solution of EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator¹³.

1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol(Riedel) was recrystallised from ethanol. A stock solution was prepared by dissolving 0.2493 gm of the dye in 100 ml of ethanol. Its strength was checked up by a photometric titration¹⁴.

Ammonium hydroxide and ammonium chloride buffers were prepared in the pH range 8-10. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. All experiments were carried out at room temperature (28±1°) and the ionic strength was maintained at 0.1±0.01 with NH₄Cl-NH₄OH buffer.

Recommended procedure for the photometric determination :

To an aliquot of the test solution containing (1-6 ml of 3×10⁻⁵ M) rare earth metal ion in a

25 ml volumetric flask, 5.0 ml of 3×10^{-4} M PAN in ethanol and 10 ml of $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl-NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer solution of pH 9.0 were added. The contents were thoroughly mixed and the total volume was made up to the mark with deionised water. The absorbance of the solution was then measured at 580 nm against reagent blank within 30 minutes of colour development.

Results and Discussion

Experiments were carried out in water-ethanol mixture since the lanthanide-PAN complexes and the reagent (PAN) are insoluble in water. The optimum composition of ethanol was found to be 20% (volume/volume). In 20% ethanol-water medium, the complex formation was found to be instantaneous and the intensity of the red colour was stable upto 30 minutes. However the solutions were found to develop turbidity on further standing.

The absorption spectra of all the lanthanide-PAN complexes in 20% ethanol-water medium at pH 9.0 showed well defined maxima at 580 nm while the reagent has no appreciable absorbance in this region.

It was found that lanthanides do not form complexes with PAN below pH 6.0. The optimum pH for complex formation was found to be 8-10. Ammonium chloride-Ammonium hydroxide buffers were found to be suitable and convenient to use in this pH range. The optimum pH range for maximum colour development for individual lanthanide complexes is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—pH RANGE, SPECTRAL PROPERTIES AND CONDITIONAL STABILITY CONSTANTS OF LANTHANIDE—PAN COMPLEXES

Metal M^{*+}	Temperature = $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$		Ionic Strength = 0.10 ± 0.01		
	pH range	λ_{max} nm	Beer's law limit, ppm	Molar extinction coefficient $\times 10^{-4}$ $\text{moles}^{-1} \cdot \text{lit. cm}^{-1}$	Conditional stability con- stant, $\log K'$
Sm	7.5-9.5	580	1.44	4.79	13.71
Eu	8.5-9.5	580	1.46	4.79	13.84
Gd	7.5-9.5	580	1.18	5.14	16.27
Tb	8.5-9.5	580	1.14	5.18	15.20
Dy	7.5-9.5	580	1.17	5.08	15.21
Ho	7.5-9.5	580	1.20	5.27	15.30
Er	7.5-10.0	580	1.20	5.42	15.47
Tm	8.0-9.5	580	1.22	5.02	15.38
Yb	7.5-9.5	580	1.25	5.05	15.27
Lu	8.5-10.0	580	1.26	5.20	15.34

The variation of PAN concentration at pH 9.0 revealed that maximum colour development was obtained when 10-15 fold excess of reagent to that of metal was present in the solution.

Under the optimum experimental conditions the lanthanide-PAN complexes obey Beer's law. The

Beer's law limits for individual metals and molar extinction coefficient values are given in Table 1.

The study of interference of various foreign substances that commonly associate with lanthanides revealed that anions such as Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , CH_3COO^- , ClO_4^- , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ have no effect on the photometric estimation even when present in 1000 fold excess to that of the lanthanide ions. $\text{P}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and F^- do not interfere with the colour formation if they are present in less than 10 fold excess. However PO_4^{3-} , EDTA, citrate and tartrate seriously interfere with the colour development even at equal concentrations to that of the lanthanides.

Ca(II), Mg(II), Cr(VI), Mo(VI) and Tl(I) do not interfere with the photometric estimation when present in 100 fold excess. Be(II), Al(III), Zr(IV), Th(IV) and V(V) do not interfere with the determination when present in less than 10 fold and in presence of excess of the reagent (PAN). However, Fe(III), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and U(VI) interfere seriously with the photometric estimation as these ions are known to form coloured complexes with PAN under experimental conditions.

Composition and Stability constants :

Investigations of Coleman, Varga and Mastin¹⁵ plots with the variation of pH and PAN concentration conclusively indicated the existence of only single absorbing species under the experimental conditions. Job's method of continuous variation¹⁶ at pH 9.0 and in 20% water-ethanol medium showed a metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 3 in all the lanthanide-PAN complexes confirming our earlier interpretation of MR_3 type of complexes with an octahedral structure where PAN is acting as bidentate ligand^{11,12}.

The conditional stability constants of the lanthanide-PAN complexes were calculated by Likussar and Boltz¹⁷ method using the expression

$$\log K' = 0.3750 - 3 \log k + \log y_{\text{max}} - 4 \log (1 - y_{\text{max}})$$

where K' is the conditional formation or stability constant of the complex, k is the sum of the total concentrations of the metal and reagent and the y_{max} is the value obtained from the normalised curve. The results of stability constants for individual lanthanide-PAN complexes were shown in Table 1.

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Effect of Aluminium Sulfate on Potassium Release and pH of Kaolinite Type Tea Soils

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CHENARY¹ reported that aluminium is well assimilated by the calcifirgedtea plants. The productivity of tea soils are being maintained by the supply of essential nutrients like nitrogen, potassium, phosphorous etc and every year 1000 kg crop of tea removed 20 kg/ha of potassium^{2,3}. It has been found that a thirteen year old tea bush utilizes 900 kg of potash per hectare every year⁴. This laboratory study attempts to see the availability of inherent potassium, in soil as effected by application of hydrated aluminium sulfate. Where symptoms of K-deficiency are apparent on the tea

bushes top dressings ranging from 200 to 400 kg/ha of muriate or sulfate of potash are suggested according to severity of symptoms. Further the study also envisages on the pH effect of aluminium sulfate⁵.

Experimental

Air-dried soil samples of specifications given in Table 1 was made to pass through a 100-mesh B.S.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL USED IN THE PRESENT STUDY

Place—Jorhat (Tooklai) 26° 47' N

Depth—0-30 cm.

(A) Aggregate analysis

Grain Size	% on a dry wt. basis
>5 mm	0.44
5-2 mm	2.33
2-1 mm	1.66
1-0.5 mm	3.43
0.5-0.25 mm	6.43
Total	14.29

(B) Mechanical Analysis (Universal Pippett Method, Piper¹⁰)

Texture	Size (mm)	% on dry wt. basis
Coarse Sand	2.000	7.55
Fine Sand	0.200	44.70
Silt	0.020	40.00
Clay	0.002	7.50

(C) Nitrogen, Carbon, Potash, Phosphate content and C/N ratio and loss on ignition analysis.

	(i)	(ii)	
Total - K ₂ O	7.4 × 10 ³ ppm	% N	0.108
Available - K ₂ O	0.09 × 10 ³ ppm	% Org.C	0.976
Total - P ₂ O ₅	0.404 × 10 ³ ppm	% Loss of Ignition	3.55
Available - P ₂ O ₅	0.004 × 10 ³ ppm	C/N Ratio	9.00

sieve and then five grams of soil was taken in aspirator bottles. The outlet of the bottles were closed with pure glasswool so that only clear supernatant solution could be taken out at pleasure. The soils were then treated with varying concentration eg. 0, 21, 63, 105 and 147 mg per 5 g soil, of BDH laboratory grade aluminium sulfate Al₂(SO₄)₃. 16 H₂O. Exchange reactions were allowed to continue at room temperature (28°) for 28 hours. The supernatant solutions were then drained out and replaced with fresh solutions of aluminium sulfate as used at 28°. Again exchange reactions were allowed to continue for 24 hours in a thermostatic waterbath controlled at 44°. The same experiment was repeated at 55°.

The pH of the extracted solutions were measured in an ELICO LI IO T pH Meter. The concentration of potassium in solution was estimated by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (Beckman 1233).

Results and Discussion

It has been found in the above study that application of aluminium sulfate to the soils lead to a

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